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The Role of Feedback When Training Pre-Service Native Language Teachers

Snezhanka D. Georgieva*

Kazan Federal University, 420008, Kazan (Russia), 18 Kremlyovskaya street

Abstract

The normatively determined competences of teachers in Bulgaria (Decree 12/01.09.2016 concerning the status and professional development of teachers, head teachers and other pedagogical specialists) prerequisite the necessity for re-evaluating the content and technological models of the pedagogic-psychological, methodical and specialized subject matter for students, who are trained to become teachers of their native language. Within the context of searching for ways of modernizing the university education of future pedagogues, the current article refers to the wide spectrum of the term *professional pedagogic competence*, summarizes the interdependence in forming the competences of the future native language teachers – academic, pedagogical (including assessment), communicative; presents reasoning for the significance of the content and technological models in competency-oriented university education, aimed at forming a certain aspect of the professional pedagogical competence, namely expert assessment. Based on studied/analyzed student's approach, with pedagogic specialties, towards the problems of feedback (in primary, secondary and higher education), an interactive model for the development of future teacher's docimological skills is offered, based on a methodical game, theatrical pedagogic situations as forms of feedback; functionality of the model is analyzed; criteria, for researching the students abilities to grade texts written by pupils, are drawn; in this regard, strategies, concerning the deficit of future teachers, are discussed. The research presents the prerequisites, stages characteristics and results of practice-tested theoretical-pragmatic model for the formation of expert assessment competence in the student, a future teacher, in the form of skills in analysing, assessing and reviewing oral and written texts by pupils, and skills in analysing pedagogic articles, concerning such assessment. The article presents and analyses several types of activities in this process, in relation to (conditionally divided) two stages, respectively: theoretical-observational – questionnaire survey of 182 students from *Konstantin Preslavsky* University of Shumen, concerning the role of feedback; empirically-effective – realization of interactive activities with 50 students for determining and improving their docimological abilities. The overall conclusions are to identify intersections between the dynamic activities (verbal and games) and the effective results in the process of interactive-reflective university training (with its essential cognitive, dynamic, communicative and affective aspects); giving reasons for the advantages of the experimental model: motivation for accomplishing results, active personal, dialogue and praxiological reflectivity, acquired confidence during assessment activities without the guidance of a university teacher, personal development in the direction of tolerance and ethics within pedagogical communication.

* Corresponding author. Tel.: +359 899 952 526; e-mail address: s.dobrevava@shu.net

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Introduction

The trends for matching the Bulgarian educational model to that of the European educational space change the perspectives for the school and university education in regards to personal and professional orientation, interactivity, pragmatization of pedagogical communication, motivation for acquiring not only cognitive knowledge, but also efficient communication strategies (including pedagogical), for studying, personal development, assessment and self-assessment. University education, which trains native-language teachers, is a socio-cultural phenomenon. At the same time it is a professional pedagogical construct, which is connected with the initial formation of the professional pedagogical competence of future teachers (within the context of its content and technological aspects); which predetermines the quality of primary and secondary education (developing a specialist in pedagogy, able to realize training in conditions, which are adequate for modern educational paradigms and are able to deal with various challenges); a construct which guarantees society's progress in humanity (within the context of its cognitive, emotional and functional realizations). Compliance of future native language teacher's training with the acting Strategy for the Development of Higher Education in the Republic of Bulgaria for the period 2014-2020 (Strategy 2014), suggests a connection between practice and theory, presupposes the trends for mutual insights and understanding of modern science and it is adequate for the modern searches and educational determinates.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of this study is theoretical deduction of the significance of native language teachers' assessment skills, as part of their professional pedagogical competence; pragmatic summary of the various feedback of future teachers, in regards to becoming expert assessors of student texts. The appointed task is solved by a number of tasks:

1. Theoretical research of the problem for the future teachers' professionalism, for feedback and its significance as an educational technology when forming an aspect of the professional pedagogical competence - expert assessment.
2. Examining the approach of students, trained for future teachers, to problems concerning feedback.
3. Drawing criteria for researching the expert assessment skills of future native language teachers.
4. Conducting an experiment for determining the functionality and effectiveness of using various feedback within competency-oriented, interactive university discourse, which prepares future native language teachers.
5. Analyzing the results from the experimental technological model.

Review of regulatory documents and relevant literature on the topic

As the Pre-school and School Education Act (PSEA, 2015) came into effect on 01.08.2018, and the new educational documents connected with it, goals, priorities and tasks for the competency-oriented Bulgarian education are defined; key competences are summarized, which are appropriate to be developed in the students during their training; characteristics of the Bulgarian teacher's professional competency are updated. In compliance with the general European trends, competences of individuals from various stages of the educational paradigm, in the context of their interdependency, are thought of as an instrument for personal development. Article No.77 from the Act regulates key competences, which are needed to be formed in students via a general education training within the Bulgarian school; first of which are competences in the sphere of Bulgarian language. The normative regulation of key competences of teachers in Bulgaria is a fact, in accordance with Application No.2 regarding Art.2, para. 2, subsec. 1 of Decree No.12 / 01.09.2016, regarding the status for the professional development of teachers, directors and other pedagogical specialists (Decree No.12, 2016), with knowledge, skills and approaches regarding four key competences: *academic competence* (suggesting initial professional training) (pedagogical, psychological, methodological and of a specialized subject) and skills for lifelong learning); *pedagogical competence* (concerning planning of pedagogical situations; organizing and leading the educational process; an adequate assessment of the student's progress); *communication competence* (based on communication skills during team work); *administrative competence* (concerning dealing with the required school paperwork). The third aspect of the pedagogical competence, represented in the regulatory documents as "Assessing the children's/student's progress, is not only interpreted as the teacher's skill to assess the student, but also to assess his/her own progress (or at least show them the way to this progress), "by creating skills in children/students for self-assessment, self-criticism and self-improvement"(Decree No.12, 2016).

In the current research this aspect of pedagogical competence is accepted as an immanent characteristic of the native language teacher's professionalism and it is defined as expert assessment.

In academic literature when characterizing the teacher's professionalism many terms are used, their definition has a broad specter and it is often achieved within the context of synonymy or hierarchy and their interdependency – pedagogical skills, professional pedagogical competence, professionalism, communicative pedagogical competence, key competences. Researchers talk about "culture of pedagogical education and behavior", "a psychological mastery when communicating", "professionally significant qualities" (Милкова, Милков, 2003: 45 – 64). As a "prerequisite and resource for developing the professional competence of the teacher", the didactic competence is updated, which is defined as "dynamic and constantly enriching and renewing system of specific, partial competences, which are interdependent and interconnected" (Vitanova, Miteva 2017).

The terms stated above, generally, point to valuable characteristics of the modern teacher. Within the image of the contemporary teacher, the professional pedagogical competence (as an equivalent to knowledge and skills in methodology, pedagogy, pedagogical psychology, pedagogical communication) will be appropriate to be accompanied with valuable personal characteristics – ethics, tolerance, compassion, rigor, goodwill; with "emotional flexibility" as a guarantee for progress and "professional success" (Asmakovets, 2015).

The broad specter of pedagogical professionalism is more conceivable within the context of the educational values of a country, of the requirements of special teaching methods of a particular school subject. In this context the research is focused on the continual and technological models in forming a

component from the native language teacher's professionalism in Bulgaria, namely expert assessment. This competence is defined as an aggregation of knowledge, skills and relations, which allow the in-service/pre-service teacher to assess the trained person in a personality-orientated context, in accordance with the assessment paradigms, by supporting the learner along the tough road to understanding and processing the deficits, by stimulating and motivating for accomplishing results and development within a personal/communicative plan. Formation of the control-assessment skills is an equivalent of knowledge about theoretic models (forming assessment, holistic assessing etc.), of acquisition of docimological criteria and scales; it is a function of skills in using various forms and methods for control and evaluation, of assessment strategies adequate to the educational constructive paradigm. The broad specter and significance of the expert assessment of the in-service/pre-service native language teacher, suggests dependency to other teacher's competences (pedagogical, psychological, private, communicative) during the time of formation, as well as during development.

In the Bulgarian methodological literature, in recent decades the necessity of changing the viewpoints for the evaluation are revealed; the importance of evaluation as a training strategy as a continuing and complementary process of learning both at school and at the university is updated. Claims are made as to the appropriateness of entering the teacher's written assessment procedures in relation to a student's written text (with their quantitative and qualitative aspects) in an effective (dispersed in time) communicative educational process of reciprocal feedback between the subjects of education, their responsibility in carrying out assessment activities (Dobreva, 2018). "The effective pedagogical manager accepts students not as passive subjects who are affected, but as active decision-makers who are developing themselves. An important point in this process is to give students constant and motivating feedback on their academic achievements, attitudes and the results they achieve" (Mavrodiev, Dimitrova, 2016). The role of accumulating life and work experience in specific situations is explained in the following context: "Every interaction, response and consequence is marked by a unique context and a situation where one gains experience and has the opportunity to learn and develop"; the focus of each training is sought not only in the competencies related to the cognitive development, but also in the accompanying emotional process (Eyubova 2018). Such theoretical-pragmatic contexts re-emphasize the importance of the problem of content and technology models in vocational university training of pedagogical learners as "a pressing need of the whole society" (Mitina, 2015).

The development of one of the aspects of this training - the expert assessment - through university education in Bulgaria is not the only equivalent of acquired knowledge on specific linguistic / methodical discipline (modern Bulgarian language, language culture, methodology of Bulgarian language education at a certain educational stage), it is not only knowledge of literary and style norms. The formation and development of the teacher's ability to evaluate the learner is not a one-time act, the result is knowledge skills, practice, experience (based on mistakes and working on them), effective exchange of feedback, it is a question of motivation of willingness and ability to assess the person next to you during pedagogical communication, his/her speech patterns, communicative behaviour. According to the author of the study, the development of expert assessment competence in university education is feasible in an interactive, reflective and game-modelled educational design; in the context of a personally developing educational environment implying synergy in the acquisition of competences (psychological, pedagogical, special subject, communicative, emotional, socio-integrative, reflexive, etc.) updating the role of evaluation based on the maximum effective synchronous use of feedback in pedagogical interaction.

Both traditional and modern educational paradigms update different forms of feedback (oral and written, direct and indirect), which are intended to provide information on the effectiveness of pedagogical interaction, the degree of realization of pre-set learning objectives, the relevance of preferred verbal and non-verbal means of achieving the objectives, of the possible changes and corrections that are to be made. Feedback, in the context of modern university language teaching of native language teachers, should be multifunctional and interdependent: to identify achievements and negative characteristics in the work of students; to predict; to correct deficits; to stimulate and support; motivate future educators for professionalism and higher performance. Through the natural way of occurrence of circumstances during the educational context that relates to university education and practices in terms of responsibilities and activities between the two educational subjects – the lecturer and the students; taking into account the multiplicity of the acquisition process of personal knowledge; with value-oriented involvement of the student in cognitive activities and activation of the educational potential of various feedbacks; with the effective use of text focusing, reflexivity, self-evaluation, motivation.

On the way to finding innovative educational practices in higher education, forming the expert assessment competence of future teachers, a two-year experimental activity was carried out with 50 students from *Konstantin Preslavsky* University of Shumen, who study for native language teachers (or for primary teachers of Bulgarian language).

Main subject of the experimental research

The main question to be answered by the experimental study is: What is the role of feedback in university education, what are the aspects of effectiveness and performance in the use of feedback in the formation of expert assessment competence of the student, trained for a language teacher?

Methodology and main stages of the research

The methodology of the study includes theoretical methods (psychological-pedagogical analysis scientific materials and normative documents); empirical methods (survey, two tests); methods of interpreting the results. In the process of experimenting with the theoretical and pragmatic model developed by the author of the research, there were joint activities of students and professors, conditionally divided into two stages, namely theoretical (theoretical-research) and empirical-resultant. The theoretical and research phase includes the activities: 1) Working with information sources - research and analysis of scientific literature and normative documents related to the problems of assessment in native language education (specific actions - collecting, juxtaposing, commenting, analysing and summarizing information). 2) Studying the opinions of students with pedagogical majors about the feedback functions in two educational contexts - higher education (through their role as trainees evaluated by lecturers in linguistic and methodological disciplines) and secondary education (through an imaginary role as future teachers); analysing the results. 3) Psychological and pedagogical testing of students' initial skills to evaluate written texts of students, analysing established basic types of errors, to present them adequately in a specific pedagogical situation; to motivate the emotional state of the individuals in the situation. The second, empirically performing stage includes: 1) Training in a non-traditional context - participation of students in methodological games, in theatrical pedagogical situations and their discussion); 2) Re-testing the students' docimological skills.

As an element in both stages there is the verification of student skills to evaluate written students' texts. The first and the second diagnostic procedure of the assessment skills of the students-pedagogues are

realized through analogous test and text formats with the production of comparable criteria (having their psychological and linguistic-methodical grounds). The criteria for determining the qualities of the expert assessment activity of the students (in accordance with the expected result of the study of several university disciplines - modern Bulgarian language, language culture, methodology of Bulgarian language and literature training in the respective educational stage) are: 1) Skills for editing deficits in written student text (indicators - spelling, punctuation, grammatical errors, measurable indicators - number / type of student-edited errors in written student texts, number / type of undetected errors, number / type of displayed errors); 2) Skills to create a review that meets the assessment's requirements (related to different aspects of the review: 2.1) its functions: *objective* (objective information for positives and deficits), motivating (stimulating pupils for further development and attainability) (informing about possible ways to overcome the deficit); 2) the subjective-objective orientation of the review).

The first diagnostic test includes an additional component - a written comment of the student, future teacher, about a non-standard pedagogical situation, as well as a summary of his emotional state in the respective situation (by presenting five keywords that describe it). In the context of non-standardization, two types of models are derived: 1) Role-play position of a teacher: evaluating pupils' texts relating to the extremes of deficiency (mass failure with a didactic task); 2) a supposed position of a pupil most often evaluated in an evaluation register other than his/her own (an excellent student receiving his/her first poor grade; a weak student receiving his/hers first excellent grade (due to diligence or copying); a student who does not understand the teacher's review; a student examining the text of a classmate (his/her best friend) and finding his/her nonconformity with the teacher's requirements and the assignment). The provocation of the non-traditional test format, examining knowledge and skills in linguistic and methodical disciplines (editing text, writing an objective review of the evaluated text) is obvious; implying the establishment of emotional states and communicative reactions of the students (taking two roles - evaluating teachers and evaluated students); providing theoretical conclusions aiming at the subsequent practical work of the university methodological training.

Activities and results

1. Questionnaire survey

The methodology of the first stage includes a survey conducted between September 2017 and October 2018 with 182 students (BA and MA) at the Faculty of Humanities and the Faculty of Education of Shumen University. Anonymous survey for reasons of objectivity has as its main task the verification of the adequacy of student understanding of feedback as a valuable pedagogical resource. The survey does not focus on the pedagogical discourse of a particular discipline; it suggests studying students' approach (in the role of responders) to the issues of communication in the educational discourse and the problems of feedback in teaching linguistic and methodical disciplines. Questions in the survey are concentrated around three problematic spheres: strategies and practices of the pre-service teachers' self-preparation; feedback functionality (used in both university and school (native language) learning; working communication models in the university's pedagogical discourse on acquiring professional competencies and their relevance to the problems of feedback. The content curriculum proposes answers in two contexts (in primary and tertiary education) and requires students to "rotate" in different positions (university students, trainers in different stages of school education).

The quantitative results obtained in the questionnaire survey point to conclusions about the awareness of students, future pedagogues, of the importance of feedback in the educational paradigms of school and university education; about the perceived multifunctionality of the teacher's review of a written

student text and its role as a form of qualitative assessment for the learner's further development in cognitive, communicative, emotional and axiological terms. Tolerated by the students forms of feedback in the university education are discussions (35, 16%), solving practical cases (18, 13%), individual or group exercises (39, 56%). As a feedback from a teacher to a student for a completed task, 27.47% of respondents prefer the review; 42.86% - individual consultation. 68.68% prefer the teacher to present information in their written review not only for deficits but also for positives. The qualitative evaluation activity of the teacher in evaluating written student text in the school respondents is related to knowledge of normative documents and criteria scales (40.11%), with an objective reflection of positives and deficits of the student text (30.77%), teacher's review encouraging and stimulating the student (23.63%). 44.50% of the students believe that inadequately used in university education are the pragmatic contexts for acquiring skills for assessment. The results of the questionnaires and the lectures held in connection with them are prerequisites of the planned and realized activities for assessment and development of the students' expertise in the assessment experiments and in the two stages of the experiment. Thus a correlation is made between the feedback patterns used in the technological model, seeking the multi-directional efficiency of their technological interdependence.

2. Theatrical pedagogical situations

The non-standard training activity during the empirical and the final stage is an addition to the traditional pedagogical practice of the lecture-seminar methodical course about key docimological concepts (measurement in native language learning, quantitative and qualitative assessment, evaluation, teacher's review, etc.). This unconventionality crystallizes into several types of personal or team activities of the students: individual work on elaboration of puppet models of character types, encountered in the practice of assessment in the Bulgarian school (the permanent weak student, the super excellent student, the excellent student with his/her first poor mark in his/her life, the weak student with his/her first excellent mark, etc.); teamwork on "naming" the created characters (Dvoyko Shestakov, Dvoyestyko, Zubrachko, Dvoiko Nepukista, Dvojko Zubarchov, Sixitzafar, etc.); participating in the role of observers of pedagogical events who need to identify relevant pedagogical subjects and justify their speech behaviour; active participation in different roles (selected by learners) of subjects from the pedagogical discourse of school assessment.

Theatrical pedagogical situations (in their method and methodological justification) provoke two types of student activities - participation in a role-play, observation and analysis of the game dialogue. Students' participation in the theatrical plays is realized in accordance with the pre-set pedagogical assessment situation (for example, evaluating the "weak student" who has received his/her first excellent mark because he/she was preparing purposefully and diligently (for the first time in his/her life) for the respective test "; assessing a "weak student who has received the first excellent mark because of the stolen answers for the test"; evaluating "an excellent student in love with hi/hers accomplishments, who received his first poor mark due to negligence to the written test"; assessing "an excellent student caught copying his homework from the Internet", etc. Playing a scene in a situation of unannounced bans or imposed stereotypes implies a natural / unregulated experience (emotional, communicative, intellectual, pedagogical and last but not least expert assessment), high emotional degree, natural activity in the game (not accepted as a training form or cold student feedback/ assessment). The emphasis in the plays is on freedom and selectivity - a free choice of pedagogical role according to their own preferences; choice of stage in which to participate; freedom of verbal and non-verbal behaviour in playing the scene, casualness of what is happening,

etc..

Only the parameters of the specific pedagogical situation are set in the experimental educational model - everything else in the imaginative pedagogical case is the consequence of personal decisions, stems from one's own judgment - a matter of choice is a meaningful, perceptive, emotional and communicative model. The feedback provided (such as spectator activity or artistic participation) to the lecturer gives endless possibilities for conclusions and subsequent reactivity in the theoretical and pragmatic educational context of university methodological training.

The visual-analytical activity during this second stage is realized in relation to several types of studies: non-verbally presented pedagogical situations by university lecturers (by theatre culture and by methodology of native language teaching) to the students in evaluating "students from the forestry school" by using hand puppets and means of proxemics, kinesiology, haptics; presented by a lecturer and students, or only by students similar to the assessment of pupils with different levels of achievability from the Bulgarian school. Students' activity at this stage is predetermined by the multiversity of the tasks: the assumption of spoken replies to the "silent" (silent, unheard) performance; a summary of the observations on the emotional state of the evaluated student; to explain the reasons for the established emotional states of the evaluator and the evaluated subject; conclusions about the adequacy / inadequacy of the reactions of these subjects (verbal and non-verbal) in the specific pedagogical situation.

Roleplaying theatrical pedagogical situations as well as their subsequent discussion are an attempt for a maximum use of different aspects of the specific pedagogical situation (communicators, message, interpersonal relationships, emotional atmosphere, pedagogical climate, feedback), multi-faceted analysis of speech in the assessment pedagogical communication - and with regard to the subject who receives it and in view of its multi-parametric impact both on the performance of the evaluated person, and on his/her emotions and behaviour.

Theoretical and practical significance of the research

The experimental technological model has been proven in two contexts - concrete pragmatic and theoretical research. The practical significance of the study consists in developing and testing a pedagogical model to develop the expert competence of future language teachers in analysing quantitative indicators as an indicator of the advantages/ disadvantages of the model. The success of the change in speech behaviour of the student, a future teacher, was measured during the period of experimental activity with results in two main contexts (static and dynamic), in the sense of changes in emotional, psychological-pedagogical and methodological aspect. Static, pragmatic output contexts allow a summary of the two main criteria for assessing the expert assessment competence of future teachers - editing mistakes, writing reviews to pupils' texts (with indicators on content, structure, formal and functional review plan) (Table No.1)

Table No.1

Results from the experimental research

Criteria for measurability of expert assessment competence	Beginning of the experiment		End of experiment	
	Number of texts	Percent	Number of texts	Percent
1. Detection/editing of abusive linguistic norms	21	42	35	70
1.1. Spelling mistakes	37	74	42	84

1.2. Punctuation mistakes	31	62	36	72
1.3. Grammatical mistakes	26	52	38	76
2. Function of the created review for an assessed student's text				
2.1. Findings	43	86	23	46
2.1.1. Information about deficits	16	32	4	8
2.1.2. Information about positives	8	16	8	16
2.1.3. Information about positives and deficits	19	38	11	22
2.2. Controlling adjustment	2	4	9	18
2.3. Stimulating	5	10	20	40

The quantitative indicators lead to the conclusion that the methodical game (imitation of specific pedagogical situations, shaping and solving pedagogical cases) and its subsequent discussion influence both aspects of the expert assessment competence. The lower result at the end of the experiment on the student's finding and editing error in pupils' written texts demonstrates the impossibility, in a short-term, even by non-traditional methodology, to overcome deficits for students, prospective teachers, in terms of unused the literal and style norms themselves. At the same time, this result implies the themes and patterns of subsequent practical work during the seminars and the linguistic and methodical disciplines. Changing the functionality of student-based reviews at the end of the experiment (in the direction of enhanced verbal explication of a control-regulating and stimulating function) and suggesting satisfaction of the achieved performance, and provoking the follow-up of the university lecturer on establishing the durability of the student's knowledge and the achieved motivation to turn it into a lasting and useful feature of their future professional practice as teachers.

Efficiency in the context of dynamics is matched by the targeted responsible involvement of the student in reflexive activities, analysis of textual production (his/her own or of a fellow student) in view of positives or deficits that need to be corrected, with a corresponding review. In this context, the criterion scale is measured by taking into account the success of the pre-service teacher's behaviour - by transforming his/her behavioral model from a passive recipient of information into a self-evaluating active and responsible for his/her further communicative development subject, who has participated in evaluating another subject. In the presented educational practice, the text reviews of the students are used in many ways - both in linguistic and didactic-methodological contexts. The deep "immersion" in the text (by the student, by the fellow student, his/her own) is accomplished through the active participation in different roles (author, editor, methodologist, teacher, pupil) and commensurate with the various functions of the modern teacher (informant, mediator, assessor, friend, coordinator, associate, counselor, diagnostician, motivator, etc.). The analysis of texts is carried out through interactive models, in the context of referencing with specific pedagogical cases and productions. Such analytical and pragmatic activities prove to be appropriate both in the process of forming different aspects of the teacher's professional-pedagogical

competency in native language and in the process of forming higher intellectual skills and moral qualities (emotional restraint, tolerant criticism, precision self-criticism, motivating selectivity, eloquent argumentation, regulating reflexivity). Explaining the monologue presented by the written reviews in oral dialogue formats (seminars, lectures, disputes, round tables) develops the skills of future teachers to work with information - to understand/ evaluate what they have written through the prisms of objectivity, adequacy, relevance, sincerity, utility; it assists mental processes to prepare, regulate and control the transformation of certain communicative and docimological knowledge into means to solve current and future professional practical tasks. If the review text is a peculiar phase/ result of the student-pedagogue's thought-speech activity, the subsequent work with the student's reviews is associated with a higher stage of reflection. The personal rethinking of main pedagogical, didactical and methodological notions in/ through students' texts, their further updating and/ or discrediting in the context of specific pedagogical situations contribute to finding the intersecting point of intellectual, personal, dialogue and praxisological reflection (Vasilev, 2006); for the effective use of the types of reflection in the formation of objective self-assessment in the current educational and future professional activity.

Reasons for the theoretical merits of the study can be found in the new pedagogical themes raised in new technological research, in the new questions posed and future discussions offered.

Conclusion

The professionalism of native language teachers to evaluate not only through the prism of acquired knowledge and acquired competencies but also through ethical guidelines and tolerant communicative paradigms is a factor for social development and personal self-assertion of the subjects of education both in the school and in the university system. The way of acquiring synchronized key pedagogical competences for contemporary pedagogues (including expert assessment, reflexive and professional communicative competence) goes through the participation of the student not only in the search, collection and recording of information, but also in activities related to making decisions about collected or suggested information; with the value-oriented engagement of the student in cognitive and social integration activities at the university on the basis of personal motivation, awareness of priorities, responsible reflexivity, objective self-esteem, self-development. In the context of established performance and acceptable content variation and technological diversity, the proposed non-variance technology model can be useful to lecturers seeking new horizons for the university pedagogical education.

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